

Study on Generalized $U_{|l|m}$ - Birecurrent Finsler Space

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Abstract: In this paper, we got the necessary and sufficient condition for some tensors to be generalized birecurrent. The relationship between the curvature tensors have been studied. Also, some results in the projection on indicatrix with respect to Cartan connection have been discussed.

Keywords: Generalized $U_{|l|m}$ -birecurrent space, curvature tensor U_{jkh}^i , projection on indicatrix.

1. Introduction

The generalized recurrent and birecurrent Finsler spaces for some curvature tensors in Cartan and Berwald senses have been studied by [3, 8, 10, 17, 18, 19, 20]. Qasem and Hadi [11-14] studied a more general Finsler space for the curvatures tensors satisfy the generalized birecurrent. The relationship between different curvature tensors were discussed by [1]. Further, the indicatrix Finsler space has been studied by [2, 5, 7, 9].

Let us consider an n – dimensional Finsler space F_n equipped with the line elements (x, y) and the fundamental metric function F positive homogeneous of degree one in y^i . The vectors y_i and y^i satisfy [4, 15]

$$(1.1) \quad a) y_i y^i = F^2 \quad \text{and} \quad b) \dot{\partial}_i y_j = \dot{\partial}_j y_i = g_{ij},$$

where the fundamental metric tensor

$$(1.2) \quad a) g_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\partial}_i \dot{\partial}_j F^2.$$

This tensor is homogeneous of degree zero in y^i and symmetric in its lower indices [16]

$$b) g_{ij} y^i = y_j \quad \text{and} \quad c) \frac{1}{2} \dot{\partial}_h g_{ij} = C_{ijk}.$$

This tensor C_{ijk} is homogeneous of degree -1 in y^i and symmetric in all its indices. Cartan's covariant derivative of the metric function F , metric tensor g_{ij} vectors $y^i y_i$, unit vectors l^i and l_i vanish identically, i.e.

$$(1.3) \quad a) F_{|l} = 0, \quad b) g_{ij|l} = 0, \quad c) y_{|l}^i = 0 \quad d) y_{i|l} = 0, \quad e) l_{|l}^i = 0, \\ f) l_{i|l} = 0, \quad \text{where} \quad g) l^i = \frac{y^i}{F} \quad \text{and} \quad l_i = \frac{y_i}{F}.$$

Cartan's covariant derivative of an arbitrary tensor T_h^i with respect to x^l is given by [6]

$$(1.4) \quad a) \dot{\partial}_j(T_{h|l}^i) - (\dot{\partial}_j T_h^i)_{|l} = T_h^r (\dot{\partial}_j \Gamma_{lr}^{*i}) - T_r^i (\dot{\partial}_j \Gamma_{lj}^{*r}) - (\dot{\partial}_r T_h^i) P_{jl}^r,$$

where $b) P_{jl}^r = (\dot{\partial}_j \Gamma_{hl}^{*r}) y^h$ and $c) P_{jl}^r y^j = 0.$

K. Yano [22] defined the normal projective connection coefficients Π_{jk}^i by

$$(1.5) \quad a) \Pi_{jk}^i = G_{jk}^i - y^i G_{jkr}^r \quad \text{where} \quad b) G_{jk}^i = \dot{\partial}_j G_k^i.$$

The connection coefficient Π_{jk}^i is positively homogeneous of degree zero in y^i and symmetric in their lower indices. K. Yano [22] denoted this tensor Π_{jkh}^i by U_{jkh}^i . Thus,

$$(1.6) \quad a) U_{jkh}^i = G_{jkh}^i - \frac{1}{n+1} (\delta_j^i G_{jkr}^r + y^i G_{jkr}^r) \quad \text{and} \quad b) G_{jkr}^r = \dot{\partial}_j G_{khr}^r.$$

The tensor U_{jkh}^i is called *curvature tensor* and G_{jkh}^i is connections of curvature tensor.

This tensor satisfies the following [21]

$$(1.7) \quad U_{jrh}^r = U_{jkr}^r = G_{jkr}^r,$$

$$(1.8) \quad U_{jkh}^i y^j = 0$$

and

$$(1.9) \quad U_{jkh}^i y^h = U_{jhk}^i y^h = U_{jk}^i, \quad \text{where} \quad U_{jk}^i = \Pi_{jk}^i.$$

The tensor U_{jk}^i is called *hv-torsion tensor* and satisfies

$$(1.10) \quad U_{jk}^i = U_{kj}^i$$

$$(1.11) \quad U_{jr}^r = G_{kr}^r$$

and

$$(1.12) \quad U_{jk}^i y^k = U_{kj}^i y^k = G_j^i,$$

where the tensor G_j^i is deviation tensor and homogeneous of degree 1 in y^i satisfies

$$(1.13) \quad G_j^i y^j = 2G^i,$$

where G^i is positively homogeneous of degree 2 in y^i . The tensor U_{jk} is called *Ricci tensor* which satisfies the following

$$(1.14) \quad U_{rkh}^r = U_{kh}$$

and

$$(1.15) \quad U_{jk} = \frac{2}{n+1} G_{jk}$$

where the tensor G_{jk} is components of the projective connection coefficients.

Douglas tensor is given by [22]

$$(1.16) \quad D_{jkh}^i = U_{jkh}^i - \frac{1}{2}(U_{kh}\delta_j^i + U_{jh}\delta_k^i).$$

$$(1.17) \quad D_{jkh}^i y^j = D_{kjh}^i y^j = D_{khj}^i y^j = 0$$

$$(1.18) \quad D_{rkh}^r = 0.$$

Definition 1.1. The projection of any tensor T_j^i on indicatrix is given by [7]

$$(1.19) \quad p.T_j^i = T_{\beta}^{\alpha} h_{\alpha}^i h_j^{\beta},$$

where the angular metric tensor is homogeneous function of degree zero in y^i and defined by

$$(1.20) \quad b) h_j^i := \delta_j^i - l^i l_j.$$

Definition 1.2. If the projection of tensor T_j^i on indicatrix I_{n-1} is the same tensor T_j^i , the tensor is called an indicatrix tensor or an indicatory tensor.

The projection of the vector y^i , the unit vector l^i and the metric tensor g_{ij} on indicatrix are given by [7]

$$(1.21) \quad a) p.y^i = 0, \quad b) p.l^i = 0, \quad c) p.g_{ij} = h_{ij}, \quad \text{where} \quad d) p.h_{ij} = g_{ij} - l_i l_j.$$

Saleem and Abdallah [19] introduced the generalized $U_{|l}$ – recurrent Finsler space. *i.e.* the tensor U_{jkh}^i is characterized by the following condition:

$$(1.22) \quad U_{jkh|l}^i = \lambda_l U_{jkh}^i + \mu_l (\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}), \quad U_{jkh}^i \neq 0.$$

where λ_l and μ_l are non-zero covariant vectors field.

2. An Generalized $U_{|l|m}$ – Birecurrent Space

Let us consider a Finsler space F_n which the normal projective curvature tensor U_{jkh}^i satisfies the generalized birecurrent property with respect to Cartan's *i.e.*

$$(2.1) \quad U_{jkh|l|m}^i = a_{lm} U_{jkh}^i + \varphi_{lm} (\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}), \quad U_{jkh}^i \neq 0,$$

where a_{lm} and φ_{lm} are non-zero covariant tensors field of second order that called birecurrence tensor field. The space that satisfies the condition (2.1) call a *aeneralized $U_{|l|m}$ – birecurrent Finsler space*. And denote it briefly by $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$.

Transvecting (2.1) by y^h , using (1.9), (1.2b) and (1.3c), we get

$$(2.2) \quad U_{jk|l|m}^i = a_{lm}U_{jk}^i + \varphi_{lm}(\delta_j^i y_k + \delta_k^i y_j).$$

Contracting the indices i and j in (2.1) and using (1.14), we get

$$(2.3) \quad U_{kh|l|m} = a_{lm}U_{kh} + \varphi_{lm}(n + 1)g_{kh}.$$

Also, in view of (1.7), the contracting of the indices i and h in (2.1), we get

$$(2.4) \quad G_{jkr|l|m}^r = a_{lm}G_{jkr}^r + 2\varphi_{lm}g_{jk}.$$

In view of (2.3) and (1.15), we get

$$(2.5) \quad G_{kh|l|m} = a_{lm}G_{kh} + \frac{1}{2}\varphi_{lm}(n + 1)^2g_{kh}.$$

Transvecting (2.2) by y^k , using (1.12), (1.3c), (1.1a), we get

$$(2.6) \quad G_{j|l|m}^i = a_{lm}G_j^i + \varphi_{lm}(\delta_j^i F^2 + y^i y_j).$$

Transvecting (2.6) by y^j , using (1.13), (1.1a) and (1.3c), we get

$$(2.7) \quad G_{|l|m}^i = a_{lm}G^i + \varphi_{lm}y^i F^2.$$

Contracting the indices i and k in (2.2) and using (1.11), we get

$$(2.8) \quad G_{jr|l|m}^r = a_{lm}G_{jr}^r + \varphi_{lm}(n + 1)y_j.$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 2.1. *The torsion tensor U_{jk}^i , Ricci tensor U_{kh} , tensor G_{jkr}^r , Ricci tensor G_{kh} , deviation tensor G_j^i , vector G^i and tensor G_{jr}^r of $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$ are non-vanishing.*

Differentiating (1.16) covariantly twice with respect to x^l and x^m in the sense of Cartan, we get

$$(2.9) \quad D_{jkh|l|m}^i = U_{jkh|l|m}^i - \frac{1}{2}(\delta_j^i U_{kh|l|m} + \delta_k^i U_{jh|l|m}).$$

Using (2.1) and (2.3) in (2.9), we get

$$(2.10) \quad D_{jkh|l|m}^i = a_{lm}[U_{jkh}^i - \frac{1}{2}(\delta_j^i U_{kh} + \delta_k^i U_{jh})] + \varphi_{lm}(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}) - \frac{1}{2}\varphi_{lm}(n + 1)(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}).$$

Using (1.16) in (2.10), we get

$$(2.11) \quad D_{jkh|l|m}^i = a_{lm}D_{jkh}^i + \gamma_{lm}(\delta_j^i g_{kh} - \delta_k^i g_{jh}),$$

where $\gamma_{lm} = \varphi_{lm}(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}) - \frac{1}{2}\varphi_{lm}(n + 1)(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh})$.

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 2.2. *In $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$, the Douglas tensor D_{jkh}^i is generalized birecurrent.*

If Douglas tensor D_{jkh}^i is generalized birecurrent and Ricci tensor U_{kh} is non-vanishing in a Finsler space, then the space is necessarily to be $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$. Then, equation (2.9), can be written as

$$(2.12) \quad U_{jkh|l|m}^i = D_{jkh|l|m}^i + \frac{1}{2}(\delta_j^i U_{kh|l|m} + \delta_k^i U_{jh|l|m}).$$

Using (2.3) and (2.11) in (2.12), we get

$$(2.13) \quad U_{jkh|l|m}^i = a_{lm}[D_{jkh}^i + \frac{1}{2}(\delta_j^i U_{kh} + \delta_k^i U_{jh})] + \gamma_{lm}(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}).$$

Using (1.16) in (2.13), we get

$$U_{jkh|l|m}^i = a_{lm}U_{jkh}^i + \varphi_{lm}(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}).$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 2. 3. *In a Finsler space F_n , if Douglas tensor D_{jkh}^i is generalized birecurrent and Ricci tensor U_{jk} is non-vanishing, then the space considered is necessarily $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$.*

3. Necessary and Sufficient Condition

We find the necessary and sufficient condition for some tensors to be generalized birecurrent in $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$. Let us consider $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$ characterized by (2.1).

Differentiating (2.4) partially with respect to y^h and using (1.2c), we get

$$(3.1) \quad \dot{\partial}_h G_{jkr|l|m}^r = (\dot{\partial}_h a_{lm})G_{jkr}^r + a_{lm}(\dot{\partial}_h G_{jkr}^r) + (2\dot{\partial}_h \varphi_{lm})g_{jk} + 4\varphi_{lm}C_{jkh}.$$

Using commutation formula exhibited by (1.4a) for $G_{jkr|l}^r$ and using (1.4b) in (3.1), we get

$$(3.2) \quad (\dot{\partial}_h G_{jkr|l|m}^r - G_{skr|l}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{jm}^{*s}) - G_{jsr|l}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) - G_{jkr|s}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) - (\dot{\partial}_s G_{jkr|l}^r) P_{hm}^s = (\dot{\partial}_h a_{lm})G_{jkr}^r + a_{lm}(G_{jkr}^r) + 2(\dot{\partial}_h \varphi_{lm})g_{jk} + 4\varphi_{lm}C_{jkh}.$$

Using commutation formula exhibited by (1.4a) for G_{jkr}^r and using (1.4b) in (3.2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \{G_{jkr|l}^r - G_{skr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{jl}^{*s}) - G_{jsr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{kl}^{*s}) - G_{jksr}^r P_{hl}^s\}_{|m} - G_{skr|l}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{jm}^{*s}) \\ & - G_{jsr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) - G_{jkr|s}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) - \{G_{jkr|s}^r - G_{tkr}^r (\dot{\partial}_s \Gamma_{jl}^{*t}) - G_{jtr}^r (\dot{\partial}_s \Gamma_{kl}^{*t}) \\ & - G_{jkr|s}^r P_{sl}^t\} P_{hm}^s = (\dot{\partial}_h a_{lm})G_{jkr}^r + a_{lm}(G_{jkr}^r) + 2(\dot{\partial}_h \varphi_{lm})g_{jk} + 4\varphi_{lm}C_{jkh}. \end{aligned}$$

Which can be rewritten as

$$(3.3) \quad G_{jkr|l|m}^r - \{G_{skr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{jl}^{*s}) + G_{jsr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{kl}^{*s}) + G_{jksr}^r P_{hl}^s\}_{|m} - G_{skr|l}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{jm}^{*s})$$

$$-G_{jsr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) - G_{jkr|s}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) - \{G_{jkr|s}^r - G_{tkr}^r (\dot{\partial}_s \Gamma_{jl}^{*t}) - G_{jtr}^r (\dot{\partial}_s \Gamma_{kl}^{*t})\} \\
 - G_{jkr|s}^r P_{sl}^t P_{hm}^s = (\dot{\partial}_h a_{lm}) G_{jkr}^r + a_{lm} (G_{jkr}^r) + 2(\dot{\partial}_h \varphi_{lm}) g_{jk} + 4\varphi_{lm} C_{jkh}$$

This shows that

$$(3.4) \quad G_{jkr|l|m}^r = a_{lm} G_{jkr}^r$$

if and only if

$$(3.5) \quad \{G_{skr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{jl}^{*s}) + G_{jsr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{kl}^{*s}) + G_{jksr}^r P_{hl}^s\}_{|m} - G_{skr|l}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{jm}^{*s}) - G_{jsr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) \\
 - G_{jkr|s}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{lm}^{*s}) - \{G_{jkr|s}^r - G_{tkr}^r (\dot{\partial}_s \Gamma_{jl}^{*t}) - G_{jtr}^r (\dot{\partial}_s \Gamma_{kl}^{*t}) - G_{jkr|s}^r P_{sl}^t\} P_{hm}^s \\
 - (\dot{\partial}_h a_{lm}) G_{jkr}^r - a_{lm} (G_{jkr}^r) - 2(\dot{\partial}_h \varphi_{lm}) g_{jk} - 4\varphi_{lm} C_{jkh} = 0.$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 3.1. In $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$, the tensor G_{jkr}^r behaves as the generalized birecurrent if and only if (3.5) holds.

Transvecting (3.3) by y^l , using (1.3c), (1.4b) and (1.4c), we get

$$(3.6) \quad y^l G_{jkr|l|m}^r = y^l a_{lm} G_{jkr}^r + y^l \varphi_{lm} C_{jkh},$$

if and only if

$$(3.7) \quad \{G_{skr}^r P_{hj}^{*s} + G_{jsr}^r P_{hk}^{*s}\}_{|m} + y^l G_{skr|l}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{jm}^{*s}) + y^l G_{jsr|l}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) - G_{jkr|s}^r P_{hm}^{*s} \\
 + \{y^l G_{jkr|s}^r - G_{tkr}^r P_{sj}^{*t} - G_{jsr}^r P_{sk}^{*t}\} P_{hm}^s - y^l (\dot{\partial}_h a_{lm}) G_{jkr}^r - 2y^l (\dot{\partial}_h \varphi_{lm}) g_{jk} \\
 - 3y^l \varphi_{lm} C_{jkh} = 0.$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 3.2. In $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$, the directional derivative of the tensor G_{jkr}^r in the directional of y^m is proportional to the tensor G_{jkr}^r if and only if (3.7) holds.

Again, transvecting (3.3) by y^m , using (1.3c), (1.4b) and (1.4c), we get

$$(3.8) \quad y^m G_{jkr|l|m}^r = y^m a_{lm} G_{jkr}^r + y^m \varphi_{lm} C_{jkh},$$

if and only if

$$(3.9) \quad \{G_{skr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{jl}^{*s}) + G_{jsr}^r (\dot{\partial}_h \Gamma_{kl}^{*s}) + G_{jksr}^r P_{hl}^s\}_{|m} y^m + G_{skr|l}^r P_{hj}^{*s} - G_{jsr|l}^r P_{hk}^{*s} + \\
 y^m (\dot{\partial}_h a_{lm}) G_{jkr}^r - y^m \partial_h (\dot{\partial}_h \varphi_{lm}) g_{jk} + 3y^m \varphi_{lm} C_{jkh} = 0.$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 3.3. In $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$, the directional derivative of the tensor G_{jkh}^r in the directional of y^l is proportional to the tensor G_{jkh}^r if and only if (3.9) holds.

Differentiating (1.6a) covariantly twice with respect to x^l and x^m in the sense of Cartan, we get

$$(3.10) \quad U_{jkh|l|m}^i = G_{jkh|l|m}^i - \frac{1}{n+1}(\delta_j^i G_{hkr|l|m}^r + y^i G_{jkh|l|m}^r).$$

Using (2.1) in (3.10), we get

$$(3.11) \quad a_{lm} U_{jkh}^i + \varphi_{lm}(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}) = G_{jkh|l|m}^i - \frac{1}{n+1}(\delta_j^i G_{khr|l|m}^r + y^i G_{jkh|l|m}^r).$$

Using (1.7a) and (3.4) in above equation, we get

$$(3.12) \quad G_{jkh|l|m}^i - a_{lm} G_{jkh}^i + \varphi_{lm}(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}) = \frac{1}{n+1} y^i \{ \{ G_{skr}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{jl}^{*s}) + G_{jsr}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{kl}^{*s}) + G_{jksr}^r P_{hl}^t \}_{|m} + G_{skr|l}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{jm}^{*s}) + G_{jsr|l}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) + G_{jkr|s}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{lm}^{*s}) + \{ G_{jkr|s}^r - G_{tkr}^r (\partial_s \Gamma_{jl}^{*t}) - G_{jsr}^r (\partial_s \Gamma_{kl}^{*t}) - G_{jkr}^r P_{hl}^t \} P_{hm}^s - 2\varphi_{lm} g_{jk} \} - (\partial_h a_{lm}) G_{jkr}^r - 2(\partial_h \varphi_{lm}) g_{jk} - 3\varphi_{lm} C_{jkh}.$$

This shows that

$$(3.13) \quad G_{jkh|l|m}^i = a_{lm} G_{jkh}^i + \varphi_{lm}(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}),$$

if and only if

$$(3.14) \quad \{ \{ G_{skr}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{jl}^{*s}) + G_{jsr}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{kl}^{*s}) + G_{jksr}^r P_{hl}^t \}_{|m} + G_{skr|l}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{jm}^{*s}) + G_{jsr|l}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{km}^{*s}) + G_{jkr|s}^r (\partial_h \Gamma_{lm}^{*s}) + \{ G_{jkr|s}^r - G_{tkr}^r (\partial_s \Gamma_{jl}^{*t}) - G_{jsr}^r (\partial_s \Gamma_{kl}^{*t}) - G_{jkr}^r P_{hl}^t \} P_{hm}^s - 2\varphi_{lm} g_{jk} \} - (\partial_h a_{lm}) G_{jkr}^r - 2(\partial_h \varphi_{lm}) g_{jk} - 3\varphi_{lm} C_{jkh} = 0.$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 3.4. In $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$, the tensor G_{jkh}^i is generalized birecurrent if and only if (3.14) holds.

Let us consider $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$ characterized by (2.2). Differentiating (1.5a) covariantly twice with respect to x^l and x^m in the sense of Cartan and using (1.3c), we get

$$(3.15) \quad U_{jk|l|m}^i = G_{jk|l|m}^i - \frac{1}{n+1} y^i G_{jkr|l|m}^r.$$

Using (2.3), (2.4) and (1.5a) in (3.15), we get

$$(3.16) \quad G_{jk|l|m}^i = a_{lm}G_{jk}^i + \varphi_{lm}(\delta_j^i y_k + \delta_k^i y_j)$$

if and only if

$$(3.17) \quad 2\varphi_{lm}g_{jk} = 0.$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 3.5. *In $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$, the tensor G_{jk}^i behaves as generalized birecurrent if and only if (3.17) holds.*

4. Projection on Indicatrix with respect to Cartan's Connection

Let us consider a Finsler space F_n for which the curvature tensor U_{jkh}^i is generalized birecurrent in the sense of Cartan, i.e. characterized by the condition (2.1).

Now, in view of (1.19), the projection of the curvature tensor U_{jkh}^i on indicatrix is given by

$$(4.1) \quad p.U_{jkh}^i = U_{bcd}^a h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d.$$

Taking the covariant derivative of (4.1) with respect to x^l and x^m in the sense of Cartan and using the fact that $h_{j|l}^i = 0$, we get

$$(4.2) \quad (p.U_{jkh}^i)_{|l|m} = U_{bcd|l|m}^a h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d.$$

Using (2.1) in (4.2), we get

$$(4.3) \quad (p.U_{jkh}^i)_{|l|m} = [a_{lm}U_{bcd}^a + \varphi_{lm}(\delta_b^a g_{cd} + \delta_c^a g_{bd})]h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d.$$

In view of (1.19) and by using the fact that $h_{j|l}^i = 0$, the equ.(4.3) can be written as

$$(4.4) \quad (p.U_{jkh}^i)_{|l|m} = a_{lm}(p.U_{jkh}^i) + \varphi_{lm}p.(\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}).$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 4.1. *The projection of the curvature tensor U_{jkh}^i of $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$ on indicatrix is generalized birecurrent in the sense of Cartan.*

Let us consider a Finsler space for which the Douglas tensor D_{jkh}^i is generalized birecurrent in the sense of Cartan, i.e. characterized by (2.11).

In view of (1.19), the projection of the Douglas tensor D_{jkh}^i on indicatrix is given by

$$(4.5) \quad p.D_{jkh}^i = D_{bcd}^a h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d.$$

Taking the covariant derivative of (4.5) with respect to x^l and x^m in the sense of Cartan and using the fact $h_{j|l}^i = 0$, we get

$$(4.6) \quad (p.D_{jkh}^i)_{|l|m} = D_{bcd|l|m}^a h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d.$$

Using (2.11) in (4.6), we get

$$(4.7) \quad (p.D_{jkh}^i)_{|l|m} = [a_{lm} D_{jkh}^i + \varphi_{lm} (\delta_b^a g_{cd} + \delta_c^a g_{bd})] h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d.$$

In view of (1.19), and by using the fact $h_{j|l}^i = 0$, the equ (4.7) can be written as

$$(4.8) \quad (p.D_{jkh}^i)_{|l|m} = a_{lm} (p.D_{jkh}^i) + \varphi_{lm} p. (\delta_j^i g_{kh} + \delta_k^i g_{jh}).$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 4.2. *The projection of the Douglas tensor D_{jkh}^i of $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$ on indicatrix is generalized birecurrent in the sense of Cartan.*

Let us consider a Finsler space F_n which the projection of the curvature tensor U_{jkh}^i is generalized birecurrent in the sense of Cartan, i.e. characterized by (2.1). Using (1.19) in (2.1), we get

$$(4.9) \quad (U_{bcd}^a h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d)_{|l|m} = [a_{lm} (U_{bcd}^a + \varphi_{lm} (\delta_b^a g_{cd} + \delta_c^a g_{bd}))] h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d.$$

Using (1.21) in (4.9), we get

$$(4.10) \quad \left\{ U_{bcd}^a (\delta_a^i - l^i l_a) (\delta_j^b - l^b l_j) (\delta_k^c - l^c l_k) (\delta_h^d - l^d l_h) \right\}_{|l|m} \\ = a_{lm} \left\{ U_{bcd}^a (\delta_a^i - l^i l_a) (\delta_j^b - l^b l_j) (\delta_k^c - l^c l_k) (\delta_h^d - l^d l_h) \right\} \\ + c_{lm} \left\{ \delta_b^a g_{cd} + \delta_c^a g_{bd} \right\} (\delta_a^i - l^i l_a) (\delta_j^b - l^b l_j) (\delta_k^c - l^c l_k) (\delta_h^d - l^d l_h).$$

Which can be written as

$$(4.11) \quad \left(U_{jkh}^i - U_{jkd}^i l^d l_h - U_{jch}^i l^c l_k + U_{jcd}^i l^c l_k l^d l_h - U_{jkh}^i l^i l_a + U_{jkd}^i l^i l_a l^d l_h \right. \\ \left. + U_{jch}^i l^i l_a l^c l_k - U_{jcd}^i l^i l_a l^c l_k l^d l_h \right)_{|l|m} = a_{lm} (U_{jkh}^i - U_{jkd}^i l^d l_h \\ - U_{jch}^i l^c l_k + U_{jcd}^i l^c l_k l^d l_h - U_{jkh}^i l^i l_a + U_{jkd}^i l^i l_a l^d l_h + U_{jch}^i l^i l_a l^c l_k \\ - U_{jcd}^i l^i l_a l^c l_k l^d l_h) + \varphi_{lm} [(\delta_j^i g_{kh} - \delta_j^i g_{kd} l^d l_h - \delta_j^i g_{ch} l^c l_k + \delta_j^i g_{cd} l^c l_k l^d l_h \\ - \delta_b^i g_{kh} l^b l_j + \delta_b^i g_{kd} l^b l_j l^d l_h + \delta_b^i g_{ch} l^b l_j l^c l_k - \delta_j^a g_{kh} l^i l_a \\ - \delta_b^i g_{cd} l^b l_j l^c l_k l^d l_h + \delta_j^a g_{kd} l^i l_a l^d l_h + \delta_j^a g_{ch} l^i l_a l^c l_k - \delta_j^a g_{cd} l^i l_a l^c l_k l^d l_h \\ + \delta_b^a g_{kh} l^i l_a l^b l_j - \delta_b^a g_{kd} l^i l_a l^b l_j l^d l_h - \delta_b^a g_{ch} l^i l_a l^b l_j l^c l_k + \delta_b^a g_{cd} l^i l_a l^b l_j l^c l_k l^d l_h]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +(\delta_k^i g_{jh} - \delta_k^i g_{jd} l^d l_h - \delta_c^i g_{jh} l^c l_k + \delta_c^i g_{jd} l^c l_k l^d l_h - \delta_k^i g_{bh} l^b l_j \\
 & +\delta_k^i g_{bd} l^b l_j l^d l_h + \delta_c^i g_{bh} l^b l_j l^c l_k - \delta_k^a g_{jh} l^i l_a - \delta_c^i g_{bd} l^b l_j l^c l_k l^d l_h \\
 & +\delta_k^a g_{jd} l^i l_a l^d l_h + \delta_c^a g_{jh} l^i l_a l^c l_k - \delta_c^a g_{jd} l^i l_a l^c l_k l^d l_h + \delta_k^a g_{bh} l^i l_a l^b l_j \\
 & -\delta_k^a g_{bd} l^i l_a l^b l_j l^d l_h - \delta_c^a g_{bh} l^i l_a l^b l_j l^c l_k + \delta_c^a g_{bd} l^i l_a l^b l_j l^c l_k l^d l_h)
 \end{aligned}$$

Using (1.9), (3.15), (1.2b) and (1.3g) in (4.11), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 (4.12) \quad & \left(U_{jkh}^i - \frac{1}{F} U_{jk}^i l_h - \frac{1}{F} U_{jh}^i l_k - U_{jkh}^a l^i l_a + U_{jk}^a l^i l_a l_h + \frac{1}{F} U_{jh}^a l^i l_a l_k \right)_{|l|m} \\
 & = a_{lm} \left(U_{jkh}^i - \frac{1}{F} U_{jk}^i l_h - \frac{1}{F} U_{jh}^i l_k - U_{jkh}^a l^i l_a + U_{jk}^a l^i l_a l_h + \frac{1}{F} U_{jh}^a l^i l_a l_k \right) \\
 & + \varphi_{lm} \left\{ \left[\delta_j^i g_{kh} - \frac{1}{F} \delta_j^i \gamma_k l_h - \frac{1}{F} \delta_j^i \gamma_h l_k - \delta_j^a g_{kh} l^i l_a + \delta_j^a \gamma_k l^i l_a l_h + \delta_j^a \gamma_h l^i l_a l_k \right] \right. \\
 & \left. + \left[\delta_k^i g_{jh} - \frac{1}{F} \delta_k^i \gamma_j l_h - \frac{1}{F} \delta_k^i \gamma_h l_j - \delta_k^a g_{jh} l^i l_a + \delta_k^a \gamma_j l^i l_a l_h + \delta_k^a \gamma_h l^i l_a l_j \right] \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since the torsion tensor U_{jk}^i is given by (2.2) and in view of (2.2), (1.3a) and (1.3c), Eq. (4.12) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 (4.13) \quad & \left(U_{jkh}^i - U_{jkh}^a l^i l_a \right)_{|l|m} = [a_{lm} U_{jkh}^i + \varphi_{lm} (\delta_j^i g_{kh} - \delta_k^i g_{jh})] \\
 & - [a_{lm} U_{jkh}^a + \varphi_{lm} (\delta_j^i g_{kh} - \delta_k^i g_{jh})] l^i l_a.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 4.3. *If the projection of the tensor $(U_{jkh}^i - U_{jkh}^a l^i l_a)$ on indicatrix is generalized birecurrent, then the space is $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$.*

Remark 4.1. *In an $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$, the projection of the U_{jkh}^i on indicatrix is generalized birecurrent, if and only if $U_{jkh}^a l^i l_a$ is generalized birecurrent.*

Let us consider a Finsler space F_n which the projection of the Douglas tensor D_{jkh}^i on indicatrix is generalized birecurrent i.e. characterized by (2.13).

Using (1.19) in (2.11), we get

$$(4.14) \quad \left(D_{bcd}^a h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d \right)_{|l|m} = [a_{lm} D_{bcd}^a + \varphi_{lm} (\delta_b^a g_{cd} + \delta_c^a g_{bd})] h_a^i h_j^b h_k^c h_h^d.$$

Using (1.21) in (4.14), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 (4.15) \quad & \left\{ D_{bcd}^a (\delta_a^i - l^i l_a) (\delta_j^b - l^b l_j) (\delta_k^c - l^c l_k) (\delta_h^d - l^d l_h) \right\}_{|l|m} \\
 & = a_{lm} \left\{ D_{bcd}^a (\delta_a^i - l^i l_a) (\delta_j^b - l^b l_j) (\delta_k^c - l^c l_k) (\delta_h^d - l^d l_h) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$+\varphi_{lm}\{(\delta_j^i g_{cd} + \delta_k^i g_{ba})(\delta_a^i - l^i l_a)(\delta_j^b - l^b l_j)(\delta_h^d - l^d l_h)(\delta_h^d - l^d l_h)\}.$$

In view of (4.15), using (1.3e) and (1.18) , we get

$$(4.16) \quad (D_{jkh}^i - D_{jkh}^a l^i l_a)_{|l|m} = [a_{lm} D_{jkh}^i + \varphi_{lm} (\delta_j^i g_{kh} - \delta_k^i g_{jh})] \\ - [a_{lm} D_{jkh}^a + \varphi_{lm} (\delta_j^i g_{kh} - \delta_k^i g_{jh})] l^i l_a.$$

Thus, we conclude

Theorem 4.4. *If the projection of the tensor $(D_{jkh}^i - D_{jkh}^a l^i l_a)$ on indicatrix is generalized birecurrent, then the space is an $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$.*

Remark 4.2. *In $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$, the projection of the D_{jkh}^i on indicatrix is birecurrent, if and only if $D_{jkh}^a l^i l_a$ is generalized birecurrent.*

5. Conclusion

The relationship between some connection coefficients for different tensors was discussed. We studied different tensors which satisfy the generalized birecurrent property. Also, we discussed the projection on indicatrix in sense of Cartan for some tensors which behaves as generalized birecurrent in $GU_{|l|m}BR - F_n$.

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